

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF THE USAGE OF ELECTRONIC DICTIONARIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Annotation

The article includes the use of electronic and paper dictionaries, their positive and negative aspects, and a separate explanation of the negative and positive aspects of electronic dictionaries by giving examples to create a fully imagination about this area in reader's mind.

Keywords

Electronic dictionary, paper dictionary, text, translator, explanatory dictionary, from one language to another language, special devices, internet, reader.

Today's world , translators are switching their work processes to the utalize of electronic dictionaries. Dictionaries are commonly used to translate texts or scientific manuals, works of art from one language to another one , or to adapt the ancient language of a certain language to the today's world. There have a different types of dictionaries, that are widely used for translation, explanatory dictionary and give a word's definition.

The first dictionaries origined in paper form, which had various positives as well as negatives .

When we speak about the paper form of dictionaries, they cover the following advantages:

- depend on reliable sources of information compiled by specialists;
- good for our eyes (1)
- doing it through a book gives a good mood to the patient, etc.

Now let's talk about the drowbacks of paper dictionaries;

They are:

- low quality of speed;
- not updating quickly;
- paper dictionaries are large and inconvenient to carry.

As we spoke above, texts translated using paper dictionaries required is time - consuming , and the lack of time prompted the creation of other types of dictionaries. As a consequence , electronic dictionaries were introduced to the public. Electronic dictionaries have been providing convenient opportunities to each of us. Even in each learning process, you can manage your own group.

Practical work like this has permitted lots of students to use translation that makes more sense out of multiple choices, and by this, all students are gaining significant opportunities to build up their abilities. If we explore electronic dictionaries in the same way as paper dictionaries, you should be sure that there are advantages and disadvantages in it. Because nothing in the world is perfect and everything has its advantages and disadvantages.

Advantages of electronic dictionaries:

- saving time;
- width of choice;
- inclusion of transcription;
- simultaneous search of the dictionary volume. (2)

Disadvantages of electronic dictionaries:

- the need for a device to use them;
- cannot be implemented without the participation of the Internet;
- damage to human eyes;

not all information is reliable.

The advantages and disadvantages of the use of electronic dictionaries in the educational system have been described above. Now, we will explain these two aspects separately.

While we always use electronic dictionaries, in the process of using them, we always repeat that saving up our time is one of its main achievements. The saved time can be used to do other things. With this, we will have a double coefficient. We explain the next place in terms of the advantages of using electronic dictionaries with the wide range of options. This allows the learner and the teacher to look up other sources when a particular word does not fit the meaning of the text. We can say that the presence of transcription is a great light on Nur, because in this process, students will get the necessary information about how to pronounce many new words. One of our last advantages is the ability to search at the same time, regardless of how many dictionary elements there are.

As there have two sides to everything, the usage of electronic dictionaries in the educational system may not have enough disadvantages. One of them is the need for a certain structure and the need for an Internet communication system to utilize electronic dictionaries. At the moment, unfortunately, the fact that Internet networks are not spread over the entire territory of our country and the slight lack of speed gives a way enough drawbacks in the field. One of the main last disadvantages of our main topic today is harming our health. This damage is

especially evident in our eyes. Therefore, some parents prefer to use paper dictionaries rather than electronic dictionaries when their children learn a certain language.

In conclusion, it should be said that every object that benefits our life has its opposite effect. That is why it is necessary to be orderly in everything we do, to use more useful aspects on our side, and to avoid negative ones.

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